

FELLOWSHIP

April 2025

Voices of Khurja

City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories, concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city’s life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens’ aspirations for the city’s future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Khurja's Heartbeat: A Journey Through the City's Core

Have you ever taken a sip of tea and put some consideration into the origin of that one simple cup of tea? And how would you react if I told you that the cup you are currently holding could have originated in my hometown, Khurja? In India, the ceramic culture is centered around this city. I invite you to accompany me on an exciting tour of Khurja, where every nook and cranny has a tale to tell about the customs and skills of the people who live there.

Come with me. Let me show you the city I call home.

INTRODUCTION

Khurja's Heartbeat: A Journey Through the City's Core

Khurja, also known as the 'Ceramic City of India,' owes its legacy to the ceramic industry. The artisans of this region, who employ techniques that have been handed down from generation to generation, produce more than just pottery; they also establish a tradition that is carried from local marketplaces to homes all over the world.

However, beyond its craftsmanship lies a city that is deeply entrenched in tradition, brought together by community, and brimming with hope for a safer and more prosperous future. Khurja is more than just a location; it is a narrative that is always evolving while still maintaining a strong connection to its history.

This document is a journey through Khurja's present, a reflection on its challenges and strengths, and a vision for a future where its heritage thrives alongside modern progress. Through the voices of its residents and the aspirations they hold, we explore how Khurja can evolve into a city of opportunity, sustainability, and pride.

On this tour of Khurja, we will explore topics that reveal many aspects of the city's character. A dialogue between the city's history, present, and future, each chapter delves deeper into the beating heart of the metropolis.

INTRODUCTION

A Morning on the Terrace:

Early morning it's quiet, peaceful. Let's go upstairs, up to the terrace. There's something about standing here, taking in the open sky and looking out at a city that has shaped me. This terrace, this space it's a privilege I've come to appreciate even more after spending the past three years in Delhi, where the skyline feels heavier, and open spaces are rare.

The weather is just right today, a perfect morning for a walk. But, not just any walk. Let's take a journey through Khurja, through its streets and corners, through the places that are not just landmarks but pieces of our hearts and minds.

Stepping into the Streets:

Stepping out of my home, we find ourselves near what we locally call the old GT Road a stretch that has long connected lives and stories in Khurja.

On our left hand as we move on old GT Road, narrow streets weave into the colony of my neighborhood, leading to homes where mornings begin with the clang of utensils and the warmth of shared greetings. We keep moving, and after about half a kilometer, Maharaja Agrasen Public School comes into view. Established in 2000, it stands as a familiar landmark, holding memories for the city's young adults.

The most cherished time in Anjla Khan's life, a 22-year-old who currently lives in Delhi, is still school. She recalls such times as the most joyful of her early years. She still misses the sense of belonging and nostalgia that school offered. Generations have walked through these gates, spent their childhood within its walls, and carried pieces of it into their futures. A little further ahead, we reach the gate to NREC College Ground.

Figure 1: NREC College Entrance
Source: Author

This college, one of Khurja oldest, has shaped countless lives. The ground, open to the public, is alive with activity—children playing, young men training, groups gathering for yoga or a morning walk. No matter the time of day, you'll always find someone here, drawn by the sense of familiarity it offers.

Sunil Pratap Singh, in his early 50s, fondly remembers the NREC College ground as a cherished neighborhood playground from his childhood. With no buildings around, it was an open space where he played cricket daily. Now, as he watches the youth enjoying the same ground, the connection to his past remains strong. For many in Khurja, this place isn't just a college; it's a part of their story, a space where friendships, dreams, and childhood memories live on.

No matter the time of day, you'll always find someone here (college playground), drawn by the sense of familiarity.

INTRODUCTION

The Heart of Khurja's Traditions

As we reach our first major turn, we arrive at one of my favorite spots—the Ramleela Ground. For most of the year, this open land is covered in blooming crops, blending seamlessly into the rhythm of everyday life. But as Ramleela season approaches, everything changes. The land is cleared, the air fills with excitement, and the city prepares for a grand series of celebrations like Dussehra, Ravan Dahan, Ram Baarat, and Kali Utsav. The Ramleela Mela is more than just an event; it's a cherished tradition, drawing not only the people of Khurja but also visitors from nearby towns and villages.

From here, we take a left and move towards one of the most recognizable roads of Khurja—the one that Google often associated with the city.

Landmarks of Education and Celebration

Now on this road, the main gate of NREC College stands tall, a landmark known to all. As we walk further, we pass several marriage halls and banquet spaces—grand, beautifully lit venues that witness the celebrations of countless families in Khurja. A little ahead, we reach NR Public School, an extension of NREC. Like Maharaja Agrasen Public School, it is one of Khurja's leading institutions, shaping young minds for years. A few more steps forward, and we find ourselves at AKP Degree College, nestled within the well-established, old colony of New Shiv Puri.

This college, with its deep-rooted history, has been instrumental in educating generations of women in the city. Continuing our walk, we soon arrived at Khurja's Government Hospital. Recently renovated after COVID-19, it now stands with a new building, offering better facilities and services. Right next to it is the Post Office of Khurja, another essential part of the city's daily workings.

And finally, a few more steps lead us to Valmiki Chowk—a place where paths, stories, and people converge, marking another important point in our journey.

INTRODUCTION

Roads Leading to Khurja's Identity

Standing at Valmiki Chowk, we find ourselves at a crossroads—four paths stretching out like branches of a tree, each leading to a different facet of Khurja's life.

The first road takes us to the main gate of Khurja city, the official entry point where the bus stand also stands bustling with travelers. Along the way, we pass a local church, a quiet and peaceful presence in the city's landscape, followed by the Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Memorial, a place of significance and remembrance. This road eventually meets the main entrance to Khurja, marking the boundary of the town.

The second road leads to one of the most popular spots in Khurja—Nav Durga Shakti Mandir. Locals often call it Bada Mandir or Devi Ka Mandir, but no matter the name, its significance remains the same. People from all over the country visit for darshan, and in recent years, it has also become a vibrant gathering place for all age groups. Just outside the temple, food stalls line the street, drawing visitors in with the aroma of fresh street snacks. Since this road continues towards Aligarh, it is commonly known as Aligarh Wala Road.

The two remaining roads are the one we came from and the one we're about to take. Buckle up—this is Gandhi Road, the very heartbeat of Khurja.

Gandhi Road – The Pulse of Khurja:

If I step out of my house for any kind of work, chances are, I'll find myself on Gandhi road. Gandhi Road is the spine of the city, connecting every corner, with the smaller streets branching off like its limbs. It's home to an incredible variety of shops, each one adding to the rhythm of daily life.

As we step forward, we soon arrive at another bustling intersection—Padam Singh Gate. A familiar landmark in the city, it serves as a branching point to different pockets of Khurja's daily life. To our left, a road leads to College Road, which eventually reconnects with the Old GT Road.

This stretch is particularly popular among students and young professionals, lined with educational institutions and the well-known Shri Ram Complex. This hub of coaching and training centers has its own legacy, shaping the academic journeys of many in the city.

On the right, a different world awaits—a maze of old colonies and historic human settlements, where generations have lived and built their lives over the years.

A Walk Through Time and Community

We continue straight, and soon, another significant religious site comes into view, surrounded by bustling shops and essential public facilities. This place, much like the temple we passed earlier, holds a special place in the hearts of Khurja's residents. A few steps ahead, we find ourselves at JAS Inter College, standing tall on our right. One of Khurja's major institutions, it has educated a vast spectrum of generations and remains a pillar of the city's educational landscape.

The area around the college is lively, with street food stalls offering tempting treats to students and passersby alike. As we leave the college behind, we continue along Gandhi Road, approaching the point where the Old GT Road begins once again. This familiar corner also leads to Khurja's local railway station, where the sound of morning train horns has long been a part of the city's daily rhythm.

*And with that, we begin to
walk through the streets,
landmarks, and discover the
everyday life of Khurja.*

INTRODUCTION

Khurja: A Brief Introduction

Khurja, also known as the 'Ceramic City of India,' owes its legacy to the ceramic industry. The artisans of this region, who employ techniques that have been handed down from generation to generation, produce more than just pottery; they also establish a tradition that is carried from local marketplaces to homes all over the world. However, beyond its craftsmanship lies a city that is deeply entrenched in tradition, brought together by community, and brimming with hope for a safer and more prosperous future. Khurja is more than just a location; it is a narrative that is always evolving while still maintaining a strong connection to its history.

Setting the Scene: What You'll Discover Here

This document is a journey through Khurja's present, a reflection on its challenges and strengths, and a vision for a future where its heritage thrives alongside modern progress. Through the voices of its residents and the aspirations they hold, we explore how Khurja can evolve into a city of opportunity, sustainability, and pride.

On this tour of Khurja, we will explore topics that reveal many aspects of the city's character. "Everyday Life in the City" captures the tempos that define everyday life, from crowded marketplaces to noisy schoolyards and the places where the most basic and profound aspects of human experience are played out. 'Places of Belonging' delves into the nooks of Khurja that contain profound emotional connections, from long-standing institutions to the locations where traditions are passed down and memories are forged. The people of "Voices of Concern" have their voices heard as they share their experiences, struggles, questions, and dreams for the future. Last but not least, "Dreams of Tomorrow" captures the hopes of the future Khurja residents who envision a better, livelier city. A dialogue between the city's history, present, and future, each chapter delves deeper into the beating heart of the metropolis.

Everyday Life

Khurja Unfolded : A Day in the life

Morning beginnings

From early morning prayers and school rushes to busy marketplaces and evening festivities, this story takes place throughout a day in Khurja. Temples, streets, and everyday life all provide light on the culture, history, and aspirations of the locals.

At the heart of the awakening of my city are the morning walkers. A large population prefer the expansive grounds of N.R.E.C. College, where a sense of nostalgia lingers in the air. Elderly residents reminisce about their childhood, recalling a time when the same grounds served as their playground, filled with laughter and innocent mischief. Walking groups, consisting of retired professionals and homemakers, engage in lively discussions—ranging from politics to the rising costs of everyday goods.

For Krishna, the volleyball at N.R.E.C. was where he learnt the game among other players. Those informal games helped him grow, finally bringing success in intra school contests. For those who live on the opposite side of the city, the Polytechnic College grounds are a favorite morning walk destination. Mr. Lokesh Kumar, in his early 40s, stated that his perfect day begins with a walk there, whilst Mr. Bhupendra has strong childhood memories associated with this area. Every morning, these areas come alive with energy and memory, bringing the city together.

While some begin their day with exercise, others head straight to the temples. The Nav Durga Shakti Mandir is among the most visited in the morning. Devotees, some with tilak on their foreheads, others walk barefoot into the sanctum, whispering their prayers to the deity. The rhythmic chants of the morning aarti fill the air, their voices blending with the distant honking of battery rickshaws. For many, these temple visits are not just about devotion; they are about belonging. Regular visitors exchange warm greetings, inquire about each other's families, and sometimes sit on the temple steps, discussing everything from harvest seasons to local employment opportunities.

Workday Hustle

As the morning progresses, the city transitions into its work mode. Schools like J.A.S. Inter College and Maharaja Agrasen Public School are bustling with students in neatly pressed uniforms, their bags filled with books and dreams. The sound of the school bell rings across the neighborhood, signaling the beginning of another day of learning.

For many parents, education is the biggest priority. Conversations in homes revolve around exams, career prospects, and the opportunities that a good education can bring. Khurja takes immense pride in its long-standing educational institutions, which have served not only the city but also neighboring towns and villages for generations.

Educational institutions in Khurja are more than just centers of learning; they are spaces that shape futures. Lokesh Kumar, now a journalist and news editor, recalls his school days at प्राइमरी पाठशाला नंबर-9, जे.ए.एस. इंटर कॉलेज, and एन.आर.ई.सी. कॉलेज, saying, 'जब भी सोचता हूं ऐसा लगता है कि कल की ही बात हो।' His journey is a testament to how these institutions continue to nurture individuals who not only build their own careers but also contribute to society.

These institutions have built a strong academic foundation and continue to be respected pillars of learning. However, in today's evolving world, there is a growing aspiration for change. The younger generation, along with educators, envisions a system that adapts to modern educational demands. There is a strong need for vocational and technical courses that can equip students with practical skills, ensuring better employment opportunities. This is especially important for those who cannot afford to move out of the city for higher education, as well as for families who, due to cultural or financial constraints, prefer their daughters to study locally. A more inclusive and future-ready education system would not only empower Khurja's youth but also strengthen the city's role as a hub of learning and opportunity.

Beyond the schools, the city's working population disperses into different directions. Some head towards government offices. Others, particularly shopkeepers and traders, move toward the local bazaars—a part of Khurja's soul. The markets hold history in their lanes, with old bazaars lined with shops that have stood for decades, serving as a comforting space for older generations. Lal Chand Verma, in his late 50s and vice principal of JAS Inter College, shares this sentiment. He recalls how his deepest childhood memories are tied to these very markets—Sarafa Bazaar, Vishaytakahana, Boora Bazaar, Anaj Mandi, Sabzi Mandi, and Bajaja Bazar—each known for its distinct trade.

प्राइमरी पाठशाला नंबर-9, जे.ए.एस. इंटर कॉलेज,
and एन.आर.ई.सी. कॉलेज, 'जब भी सोचता हूं ऐसा
लगता है कि कल की ही बात हो।'

*(Primary School No.9, JAS Inter College
and N.R.E.C. College- whenever I think
about them, I feel it was like yesterday.)*

-Lokesh Kumar

Places of Belonging

Credit: Sachin Gawade, Unsplash

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Voices of Khurja:
A Vision for future

Khurja's Embrace : Spaces of Connection

As the sun dips below the horizon, Khurja truly comes alive. The streets near Nav Durga Shakti Mandir transform into a paradise for food lovers. Families and groups of friends gather here, their conversations blending into the bustling sounds of street vendors. Kavita Sharma, in her early 40s, describes it as the go-to spot in a city with limited entertainment options. *“There’s not much to do here,” she shares, “but yes! you can head to Shakti Mandir for street food and to socialize.”*

For the people of Khurja, street food is not just about eating—it’s an experience, a ritual, and a connection to home. Many of those I interviewed, who now live outside the city, shared how their ideal day back in Khurja would always include spending time at their favorite street food stalls, reliving memories of carefree days spent with friends over plates of chaat, tikki, and momos. Even for those who live in the city, street food is an essential part of daily life—whether it’s a quick afternoon snack or an evening spent chatting over steaming plates of pav bhaji and samosas.

Figure 2
Source: Author

These bustling food spots are more than just eateries; they are social spaces where people gather, friendships are strengthened, and nostalgia lingers in the air. No visit to Khurja feels complete without indulging in the flavors that define its streets, making street food one of the most beloved and fun aspects of life in the city. Religion and culture are deeply woven into the fabric of Khurja, shaping its identity and bringing the community together in ways that go beyond faith.

Siddheshwar Mandir, one of Khurja's oldest temples, with a strong sense of tradition and devotion. A huge pond beside it adds to its calm attractiveness, attracting people all year. On Shivratri, the temple comes alive with a large number of believers, producing a sense of faith and joy. For many people, visits to Siddheshwar Mandir evoke childhood memories of walking around the bustling mandi with their father or grandfather, taking in the sights, sounds, and spirituality of the site.

For Ajeet Kumar, now in his 50s, the Siddheshwar Temple remains one of the strongest imprints of his childhood. He recalls how this temple, along with the Ramleela Maidan, was a constant presence in his younger days, a space that still pulls him back in nostalgia. *“जब भी यहां आता हूं, पुरानी यादें ताजा हो जाती हैं।”*

“मेरे बचपन की सबसे गहरी यादें मेरे शहर में सिद्धेश्वर मंदिर से जुड़ी हैं।”

But these places are not just relics of the past—they continue to shape the experiences of newer generations. Krishna Sharma, 21, shares how his father and grandfather used to take him to these very temples, making them more than just places of worship. They became a bridge between generations, a living tradition that connects family members across time.

Ramayan ki Jhalak, Mela ka Anand

Ram Leela Mela is a grand celebration that holds immense cultural and emotional value for the city. Preparations for it begin months in advance, with different neighborhoods coming together to plan performances, set up elaborate stages, and organize vibrant processions. It is not just a retelling of a mythological tale; it is a moment when generations unite, as elders recall past performances and children watch in awe, experiencing the magic for the first time.

Beyond Ram Leela, Khurja's true spirit lies in its inclusivity and unity. The city is home to a diverse mix of people—across class, caste, and religion—who coexist in harmony, making it a place where faith is not just practiced but respected by all. Every festival is celebrated with the same enthusiasm and communal spirit. The streets light up with processions, rallies, and collective prayers, where people from all backgrounds come together—not just as observers but as active participants in each other's traditions.

This culture of mutual respect and shared celebrations is something truly special about Khurja. It is not just about religious devotion but about the collective joy of community life, where every festival, big or small, is an opportunity to strengthen bonds and embrace the city's rich diversity.

These spaces—temples, community grounds, and cultural sites—are where Khurja breathes, where people don't just visit but belong. They are places where festivals are celebrated, stories are passed down, and where the city's past and present merge seamlessly into everyday life.

Voices of Concern

Echoes of Khurja : Concerns that matters

The Missing Spaces

However, while Khurja's traditions remain strong, there is a growing aspiration for modern recreational spaces. Residents, especially the younger generation, voice their need for parks, playgrounds, and a proper movie theater—places where they can unwind and create new memories. Many believe that such spaces will not only enhance the city's social fabric but also provide healthier avenues for leisure and community bonding.

Kavita Sharma highlighted the absence of movie theaters and well-planned public areas, noting that these gaps make the city feel incomplete. *“Medical facilities are inadequate, and there are no proper recreational spaces like cinemas where people can unwind,”* she shared.

While Khurja has seen the growth of cafes and parks in recent years, these changes primarily cater to young adults. Riddhi Agrawal and Anjla Khan, both in their early 20s, reflected on how the city has evolved since their school days. *“We now have more places to hang out compared to before,”* they shared. However, they also pointed out a significant gap—parents with young children still struggle to find entertainment options for their kids.

Without a dedicated stadium, aspiring athletes have limited opportunities to train and compete at a higher level. The city also lacks well-maintained parks, sports facilities, and open spaces, leaving residents—especially the youth—with fewer avenues for physical activity and social engagement. This gap in infrastructure not only affects sports development but also limits recreational spaces for the general public.

“The biggest shortcoming in our city is the absence of a proper sports stadium, and even medical facilities are not up to the mark.”
-Ajeet Sharma

Unemployment

The Khurja Sabzi Mandi, bustling with traders, vendors, and laborers, reflects this vibrant market culture, where people work tirelessly to keep the city's economy moving. However, despite this constant activity, employment opportunities remain limited, still largely reliant on traditional industries, particularly pottery—the city's enduring economic backbone.

Figure 3
Source: Author

Residents—especially those in need of immediate income often turn to labor work in pottery as their only option. While this industry has long shaped Khurja's economy, it has also evolved over time. Mr. Sunil Pratap Singh, reflecting on these changes, shared, *“In my childhood, fewer potteries were running in the city. Now, the number has grown significantly. A lot of labor is now done by machinery, including the bhatti. Back then, when coal was used for cooking ceramics, people found work loading coal into the bhatti.”*

With mechanization reducing manual labor, the city urgently needs diversification to create new and sustainable employment opportunities beyond pottery.

With ample labor force and available space, Khurja holds strong potential for new industries, businesses, and employment projects. The introduction of manufacturing units, service-based industries, or corporate investments could create alternative job opportunities, reducing the city's heavy dependence on pottery work.

Mr. Ashok Kumar Arya echoed this sentiment, emphasizing that economic diversification is key to tackling unemployment. He pointed out that while a large section of the population relies on agriculture and pottery, these sectors alone cannot sustain livelihoods year-round. His solution? Encouraging industrial expansion and business investments that can harness the city's workforce while utilizing available land for development.

This growing concern among locals reflects the need for strategic economic planning, ensuring Khurja moves towards a more sustainable and prosperous future.

Stuck in the Jam

Krishna Sharma, who now resides in Noida but frequently visits his hometown, Khurja, shared a challenging experience that many locals can relate to. He mentioned how, when traveling back to Khurja by car, he schedules his time carefully because of the constant traffic congestion. The roads, often narrow and overcrowded, make driving in and around the city a time-consuming struggle. Adding to this, Lokesh Kumar highlighted specific choke points, stating,

शहर में जाम काफी लगता है, खासकर जेवर अड्डा, कबाड़ी बाजार, ककराला चौराहा तथा शहीद दाताराम चौक।

He believes that a well-planned initiative by the administration could help ease these traffic problems, making daily commuting much smoother. As he puts it, "प्रशासन द्वारा तैयार की गई एक अच्छी कार्य योजना इस जाम को खत्म करा सकती है जिससे कि आवागमन सुगम हो सकता है।"

Additionally, another concern was raised by a resident about the state of Khurja roads and encroachments. Mr. Lal Chand Verma pointed out, "मेरे विचार से यहां की जलनिकासी और सड़कों का चौड़ीकरण करना जरूरी है। शहर की अति व्यस्त सड़क गांधी रोड, कचहरी रोड, सुभाष रोड अतिक्रमण के कारण अपनी पुरानी पहचान खो बैठी हैं।" These once-efficient roads are now struggling under the pressure of increasing traffic and encroachment, making movement more difficult for residents and visitors alike.

These personal accounts demonstrate how traffic congestion is still a major problem in Khurja, impacting both locals and tourists. In addition to making regular travels difficult, the city's congested roads and high car density also impede seamless connectivity. With improved road infrastructure, traffic control, and administrative involvement, a planned approach to urban planning might greatly increase mobility and raise Khurja's general livability.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Khurja's Future : Vision of Tomorrow

Modernizing Farming in Khurja

Mr. Kapil Kumar Gupta who works in Khurja's Sabzi Mandi highlighted the untapped potential of the city's agricultural industry. While many people in Khurja and the surrounding areas are involved in farming, there is a gap in knowledge and modern techniques. Farmers continue to rely on traditional methods, which often lead to lower yields and inefficient use of resources.

Mr. Ashok Kumar Arya, reflecting on the struggles of local farmers, shared, *"A big part of the population is involved in agriculture, but it's not filling their stomachs, and they are not employed all year round."* The cultivation of sugarcane and rice remains seasonal, leaving many without stable incomes.

With the right workshops, training programs, and guidance, farming in Khurja could become more productive and profitable. There is a strong workforce capable of handling agricultural activities, but they need access to modern tools, smarter irrigation techniques, and better market strategies to truly thrive. If agricultural initiatives were introduced—whether through government support, private investment, or educational programs—it could open new avenues for employment and strengthen the local economy beyond pottery and manual labor.

Bridging the Healthcare Gap

Khushhali, a 21-year-old resident of Khurja, shared her struggle with chronic medical health issues. Due to the lack of adequate healthcare facilities in Khurja, her parents often had to take her to different cities for treatment. This personal experience highlights a significant concern for many residents in Khurja, where access to specialized medical care, especially for chronic conditions, is limited.

This issue is not isolated to Khushhali alone. Many others in Khurja face similar difficulties, relying on external medical facilities, which can be both financially and emotionally draining for families.

Many female participants criticized Khurja's lack of women-specific health care. Riddhi Agrawal, another 21-year-old, noted the lack of gynecologists and female health services, notably for maternity and childbirth. Due to this lack, Khurja women must travel to larger cities for basic medical consultations and delivery services, which is difficult and costly. Many people of Khurja want a women's health center or more specialist doctors because it directly affects women's health. Mrs. Kabita Sharma noted that while Khurja hospitals have improved in space and facilities, the city lacks trained medical experts and specialized services to adequately utilize this infrastructure. There is room for growth, but without trained doctors, especially in gynecological and maternity care, healthcare quality is limited. Many locals underlined that improving healthcare in the city requires more than just building new hospitals or increasing spaces—it requires well-trained professionals to provide high-quality medical treatment. Improved infrastructure and medical knowledge are needed to solve the city's healthcare issues and protect citizens.

Figure 4
Source: Author

Conclusion

Khurja's story is one of continuity and change, of reverence for the past and enthusiasm for the future. The city's heart beats in its temples, markets, and streets, but its future lies in the aspirations of its people. While traditions remain at its core, there is a collective vision for a city with more public spaces, improved facilities, and a vibrant social life.

The everyday lives of Khurja's residents are shaped by age-old customs and modern struggles. From the pottery industry that has defined the city's identity for generations to the bustling sabzi mandis that keep its economy running, Khurja thrives on its hard working population. However, challenges remain—limited employment diversification, inadequate healthcare facilities, and urban congestion continue to hinder its full potential.

The need for better public spaces, modernized education, and improved healthcare access is a recurring concern, highlighting the gaps in the city's infrastructure and services. Aspirations for a more connected, efficient, and opportunity-rich Khurja are evident in the voices of its people. The agricultural sector holds untapped potential, yet it lacks access to modern tools and training.

The healthcare system, while improving in infrastructure, still struggles with a shortage of specialized medical professionals, particularly for women's health. Traffic congestion, encroached roads, and inadequate transport planning continue to affect the city's livability. The solution lies in strategic planning, investment in human capital, and policy-level interventions that prioritize the well-being of Khurja's residents.

Despite these challenges, the city's spirit remains strong. Khurja is not just a city of past legacies but of unwritten futures. A collective effort from the government, local leadership, and the community can transform these aspirations into reality—ensuring that Khurja grows into a city that provides better opportunities, greater mobility, and a stronger sense of belonging for all. The journey ahead is one of resilience and innovation, where each step forward builds a more prosperous, inclusive, and thriving Khurja.

Conclusion

The voices of Khurja’s citizens—whether young students, aging shopkeepers, or families carrying decades of memories—are clear. They seek progress that respects history, development that nurtures community, and a future where Khurja thrives as a place of both comfort and opportunity. The story of Khurja is still being written, with every sunrise bringing new aspirations and every sunset carrying the whispers of dreams yet to be fulfilled.

Figure 5
Source: Author

This document was created with the assistance of AI tools, including ChatGPT, for tasks such as drafting, summarizing, and refining text. All content has been reviewed and edited to ensure accuracy and originality.

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Isha Arya

Isha is from Khurja, the Ceramic City of India. She is a Sociology honors student at Lady Shri Ram College for Women, Delhi University. As a Cadet of the National Cadet Corps (NCC), she embraces the values of leadership and teamwork. Isha is also passionate about learning languages, which she believes enrich her understanding of different cultures. She values artistic interests that offer her expressing herself in unique ways. After her undergraduate studies, she plans to pursue a master's in Area Studies, specifically focusing on Southeast Asia, to deepen her academic expertise and contribute meaningfully to her field.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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